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Psychometrics Of An Alternative Instrument For Experimental Skill Assessment Among Biology Students In Senior Secondary Schools In Taraba State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study was carried out to develop and validate psycho-productive test for assessing practical skills of biology students in Taraba State, Nigeria. The study employed the use of instrumentation design. The study's population was 15,142. These were students from 346 secondary schools. The sample for the study was 1,013 senior secondary school II (SSS II) students. Stratified purposive sampling technique was used. The alternative instrument developed for experimental skill assessment is known as Practical Skills Assessment Test (P-SAT). This contained 162 multiple choice items which were also analyzed in the study. Psychometric analysis on P-SAT revealed an excellent difficulty index of 0.53. Item discrimination of P-SAT indicated an excellent discrimination of 0.451 on the average with no negative index, however, 12(7.4%) items are found to discriminate poorly. Distracter Analysis of P-SAT revealed 3(1.85%) items have nonfunctional distracters, 26(16.04%) items have negative distracters. Therefore, a total of 36 (22.22%) items out of the 162 items analyzed did not qualify to be listed into P-SAT and should be discarded or revised and further analyzed. Thus P-SAT was reduced to a total of 126 (77.78%) items. It was therefore recommended that Test experts, school authorities and relevant stakeholders should adopt methods employed in this research to train Biology teachers to enable them perform psychometric analysis on test items. It was also recommended that teachers should adopt the use of P-SAT as a valid and reliable question bank for students' practical skills assessment thereby minimizing the effects of challenges posed by total lack or insufficiency of laboratory apparatuses in Biology Laboratories.

Keywords: Psychometric Analysis, Item Difficulty; Item Discrimination; Distracter Efficiency; Practical Skill Assessment Test (P-SAT)

INTRODUCTION

Despite the importance of Biology activity-based assessment which accords secondary school students the opportunity to acquire skills for application in industry and a vast number of other professions, teaching and assessment of practical Biology in secondary schools in Nigeria has continue to be fraught with challenges of inadequate laboratory apparatuses causing Biology assessment to fall short of their skill assessment expectation (Josiah & Gana, 2019). There has been a tremendous growth in students' population without a corresponding growth in the number of facilities for assessment of skills as a result of economic depression and corresponding rise in cost as suggested by Osuji (2016). The absence of these facilities often leave teachers and test experts in a state of inactivity as they find it difficult or practically impossible to improvise (Babajide & Peter, 2021). This

lack of functional Biology laboratory and inadequate equipment for Biology practical in most Nigerian secondary schools as stressed by Aderonmu and Obafemi (2015), is hampering laboratory activities and assessment of skills.

Studies have also shown that secondary education systems in developing countries as opined by Null et al. (2017), are under pressure to serve more students and to do so more effectively. Secondary schools often lack necessary teaching facilities and assessment equipment (Tety, 2016). This challenge is compounded by the country's economic situation which makes the standard laboratory apparatus unaffordable to most schools as most of the schools have acute shortages of instructional materials. Particularly, most schools in Nigeria seem to have scarcity of physical facilities and instructional materials therefore Biology teachers are often faced with the challenges of activity-based teaching and assessment of skills (Ajemba et al., 2021; Danjuma & Adeleye, 2015; Lyimo et al., 2017).

In the face of this shortfall and the rising call for alternative assessments for Biology achievement which grows out of the current constructivist reform in science, therefore, the need for a standardized Biology skill test for assessing psychomotor objectives of the curricula (Adebisi, 2021; Okeme & Bishie-Unung, 2015; Suhendi et al., 2018). This alternative test is termed Practical Skill Assessment Test (P-SAT). Experimental skills are requisite skills for executing tasks in industries and in many other professions. To Osinem and Nwoje (2015), they are manipulative or technical skills needed for performance in any given occupation which could be acquired through observation, training and learning. Experimental skills are manipulative skills or motor skills which are required to perform certain activities efficiently (Osinem, 2018; 2020).

Measurement properties, in psychometrics, are considered the characteristics of an instrument that describe its validity, reliability and responsiveness. These qualities are therefore commonly known as the 'psychometric properties' of an instrument. It should be noted that validity or reliability are not immutable characteristics inherent to a measurement instrument. Instruments possess varying levels of these properties, which are influenced by the construct or factor they are measuring, the context in which they are being applied, how they are used and what the scores generated by the instrument are being used for. A grasp of psychometrics is therefore essential in good measurement practice. The term psychometrics arises from disciplines that were early adopters of scale and instrument creation, where decisions were based on measurement and clinical evaluation – psychology and education (Streiner, 2003). Psychometrics owes its methodological heritage to these disciplines, and is where key measurement theories such as classical test and item response theories originated (De Vet et al., 2011). Both Item Response Theory and Classical Test Theory are methods for estimating instrument's scores and measuring patient traits. Notwithstanding, these two theories differ in their approach and underlying theoretical assumptions (Swan et al., 2023).

Purpose of the Study

- i. To determine the difficulty index of P-SAT
- ii. To determine the discrimination index of P-SAT
- iii. To determine the distracter efficiency of P-SAT

Research Questions

- i. What is the difficulty index of P-SAT?
- ii. What is the discrimination index of P-SAT?
- iii. What is the distracter efficiency of P-SAT?

Concept of Item Difficulty, Item Discrimination and Distracter Analysis

The item difficulty, also called item facility, is the percentage of students that correctly answered the item. The difficulty index ranges from 0.00 – 1.00. The higher the difficulty index, the easier the item is understood to be (Anigbo, 2015). Item difficulty, as posited in Eaton et al. (2019), relates to the probability that students will answer the item correctly. The harder an item is the larger the item difficulty will be and vice versa. Thus, an item with a difficulty of 2 is harder than an item with a difficulty of -2. Yumelking (2019) argued that a good test items is an item that is not too easy and too difficult. A too easy item does not stimulate students to pay more effort to finish it. Otherwise, a too difficult item will cause the students to become less motivated to try again because it is out of their reaches to finish it. Item difficulty is computed as the number of correct responses in both the strong group and the weak group is divided by the total number of students in both sets and then multiplied

by 100. The total percentage of the individuals who answer the question adequately is known as the difficulty coefficient denoted by P, which is always a positive number and ranges from 0 to 100 (Ivanova & Voynikova, 2021).

Item difficulty may be viewed as a measure of the fraction of test-takers that correctly answered an item. Item difficulty index, also commonly referred to as p-value, is a measure of the fraction of the whole test-takers that correctly responded to an item (Uduafemhe et al., 2021). Difficulty index of an item as stated in Okoye and Ndubuzor (2021), is the proportion of the subjects that got that item right. It actually tells us how easy the item was for the students in that particular group. The higher the difficulty index the easier the question and the lower the difficulty index the more difficult the question. Item difficulty is the percentage of students who answered an item correctly. The range of items difficulty can be categorized into difficult, moderate, and easy. Easy and difficult items were reported to have very little discrimination power (Rezigalla, 2022).

Item difficulty shows the overall proportion of examinees that accurately answered an item. An item is considered easy when a large proportion of examinees accurately answer an item (Butakor, 2022). Item Difficulty index of an item is usually calculated by the mathematical expression; Difficulty index (P) = $[(H + L)/N] \times 100$. P is the item difficulty index, H is the number of students answering correctly in high achievers group, L is number of students answering correctly in the low achievers group and N is the total number of students in both groups including non-responders. When $P \leq 30\%$ item is usually interpreted as difficult, If $P = 30 - 70\%$ item is interpreted as acceptable and when $P \geq 70\%$ item is interpreted as easy (Teli & Nilesh, 2022).

Item discrimination is another key parameter of item analysis. It explains how well an item can differentiate among examinees with different ability. A good item, then, is the one that favors the higher achievers while not favoring the lower achievers. The discrimination values of a good test item ranges between 0.5 to 2 and the steeper the slope of an item characteristic curve, the higher an item's discrimination values. The Item discrimination value above 1 is normally desirable for a good test item and discrimination values above 0.75 can also be acceptable (Anigbo, 2015; Bichi & Talib, 2018). A negative discrimination index may indicate that the item is measuring something other than what the rest of the test is measuring. More often, it is a sign that the item has been mis-keyed. Such items should be revised or eliminated (Baidoo-Anu, 2019). Item discrimination is a measure that differentiates between the performance of students in the high score group and those in the low score group. The larger an item's discrimination the better it is at placing a student above or below a specific latent ability scores. Functionally, item discriminations should be relatively large for all of the items on the assessment (Eaton et al., 2019; Uduafemhe et al., 2021).

Discrimination index can take values from -1.00 to $+1.00$. When the degree of item discrimination is high, the best learners most often answer correctly, while the weak ones, incorrectly. If the coefficient is close to zero, then both groups of students are equally likely to get the answer right, and if the coefficient is -1 , then the weak students manage to supply a correct answer, and the better prepared ones do not. The reasons for this may be different, but most often very low item discrimination is due to unclear formulation of the test questions and therefore they have to be edited or altogether removed from the test (Ivanova & Voynikova, 2021). Negative discrimination index reflects that lower achiever examinees answer the item more correctly, while zero discrimination indicates equal numbers of students in the upper and lower groups. Negative discrimination is thought to be due to item flaws or inefficient distractors, miss keys, ambiguous wording, gray areas of opinion, and areas of controversy Rezigalla, 2022). Discrimination index from 0 to 0.19 indicates poor discrimination. An item with a discrimination index of 0.2 to 0.29 is considered to have an acceptable discrimination, Items with discrimination index between 0.3 to 0.39 is said to be of Good discrimination while items with discrimination index of greater than or equal to 0.4 is considered to be of excellent discrimination (Teli & Nilesh, 2022).

Another useful step in reviewing the effectiveness of a test item is by performing distracter analysis. Distracter evaluation is a step which ensures that all incorrect options, or distracters, are actually distracting as it should. In order for a distracter to be acceptable it should attract at least one candidate. If no one selects a distracter it is important to revise the option and attempt to make the distracter a more plausible choice (Baidoo-Anu, 2019). Distracter analysis is not interested in how the test takers select the correct answer, but how the distracters were able to function effectively by drawing the test takers away from the correct answer. The number of times each distracter is selected

is noted in order to determine the effectiveness of the distracter (Asamoah & Ocansey, 2019). Among item's alternatives, only one is the key answer and others are called distracters. Distracters should appear similar to the key in terms of the used words, grammatical form, style, and length. It is a measure of how well the incorrect options in an item prevent the 'not-so-bright' test-takers from picking the right option. Good distracters appeal to a higher proportion of low-achieving test-takers than they do to the bright ones, in that way they result in negative statistics (Rezigalla, 2022; Uduafemhe et al., 2021).

A distracter is good when the relative proportion of students in the weak group who selected it is greater than the relative share of the students that chose it in the strong group. It is effective when its discrimination is negative and less than - 0.20 (Ivanova & Voynikova, 2021). A distracter is considered to be a good distracter when it attracts more examinees from the group of low achievers than the group of high achievers. A distracter that fails to "attract any examinees is dysfunctional, does not assist in the measuring of educational outcomes, adds nothing to the item or the test (psychometrically) and has negative impact upon learners". There are two types of distracters. These are non-functional distracter and functional distracter. Nonfunctional distracter in an item, is the option, other than the correct option selected by less than 5% of students and the functional or effective distracter is the option selected by 5% or more (Sharma, 2021; Teli & Nilesh, 2022).

RESEARCH METHODS

This study employed the instrumentation research design. This design is also known as Research and Development design (R&D). The study was carried out in Bali, Jalingo and Wukari Education Zones in Taraba State, Nigeria. The population for this study is 15,142 from the 364 secondary schools in Taraba State. This comprised of all students in senior secondary school II (SS II) in public senior secondary schools in Taraba State. 8,392 of this population are males and 6,750 are females (Taraba State Ministry of Education, 2023). The sample size was 1,013 SS II students. Stratified purposive sampling technique was used.

P-SAT consisted of 162 multiple choice items. Each question has four distracters and one key. P-SAT was developed using Biology curriculum for senior secondary school students where practical skills are predominant. Three content areas used. These areas included Ecological Techniques with 55 items, Biological Instrumentation and Safety with 55 items, then, Food and Digestive Enzymes with a total of 52 items. This development was based on the table of specifications and Simpson's levels of psychomotor domain (Simpson, 1972 as cited in Okeme 2015; Ukonze 2019). P-SAT was developed with levels which included Perception with 48 questions, Set with 18 questions, Guided Response with 14 questions, Mechanism with 19 questions, Complex Overt Response with 25 questions, Adaptation with 24 questions and Origination with 18 questions.

In an effort to establish validity of P-SAT, three experts were selected from the Faculty of Education, Taraba State University Jalingo. The experts were selected based on their area of expertise, level of education and years of experience. To establish face validity, these experts evaluated P-SAT based on the items' interface, structure of sentences, grammar and other issues which may create ambiguity for respondents. Critiquing and suggestions were made and these were strictly considered to attain face validity. Administration of P-SAT was done in 10 public secondary schools across the three Education Zones used in the State. Permission was sought from the school authorities and two experienced research assistants were used in each of these sample schools. A session of brief discussion on the research objectives was held with the research assistants who are also experienced teachers who are well familiar with the students. The students commenced at the same time and ended after 2 hours and forty-five minutes.

Research Question 1: *What is the difficulty index of the items of P-SAT?*

Table 1: Difficulty Analysis of the items of P-SAT

Item	Difficulty	Item	Difficulty	Item	Difficulty	Item	Difficulty
q1	0.53	q44	0.50	q87	0.48	q130	0.39
q2	0.65	q45	0.63	q88	0.65	q131	0.57
q3	0.51	q46	0.43	q89	0.48	q132	0.41
q4	0.65	q47	0.59	q90	0.61	q133	0.37
q5	0.52	q48	0.46	q91	0.53	q134	0.56
q6	0.62	q49	0.42	q92	0.49	q135	0.44
q7	0.57	q50	0.63	q93	0.60	q136	0.59
q8	0.52	q51	0.47	q94	0.46	q137	0.41
q9	0.62	q52	0.65	q95	0.61	q138	0.57
q10	0.49	q53	0.43	q96	0.45	q139	0.55
q11	0.61	q54	0.64	q97	0.44	q140	0.46
q12	0.43	q55	0.53	q98	0.58	q141	0.56
q13	0.46	q56	0.50	q99	0.50	q142	0.41
q14	0.61	q57	0.62	q100	0.66	q143	0.50
q15	0.51	q58	0.46	q101	0.43	q144	0.45
q16	0.64	q59	0.64	q102	0.65	q145	0.57
q17	0.50	q60	0.46	q103	0.52	q146	0.43
q18	0.63	q61	0.44	q104	0.47	q147	0.55
q19	0.56	q62	0.61	q105	0.58	q148	0.45
q20	0.51	q63	0.48	q106	0.43	q149	0.41
q21	0.62	q64	0.66	q107	0.61	q150	0.55
q22	0.46	q65	0.50	q108	0.42	q151	0.46
q23	0.67	q66	0.59	q109	0.42	q152	0.55
q24	0.47	q67	0.54	q110	0.60	q153	0.46
q25	0.46	q68	0.49	q111	0.46	q154	0.53
q26	0.64	q69	0.58	q112	0.63	q155	0.50
q27	0.49	q70	0.46	q113	0.46	q156	0.49
q28	0.66	q71	0.57	q114	0.58	q158	0.41
q29	0.48	q72	0.44	q115	0.55	q159	0.51
q30	0.68	q73	0.44	q116	0.51	q160	0.50
q31	0.54	q74	0.61	q117	0.58	q161	0.54
q32	0.52	q75	0.51	q118	0.43	q162	0.49
q33	0.63	q76	0.65	q119	0.56		
q34	0.46	q77	0.43	q120	0.43		
q35	0.61	q78	0.61	q121	0.43		
q36	0.48	q79	0.53	q122	0.63		
q37	0.47	q80	0.49	q123	0.48		
q38	0.64	q81	0.59	q124	0.58		
q39	0.47	q82	0.47	q125	0.44		
q40	0.67	q83	0.59	q126	0.58		
q41	0.46	q84	0.45	q127	0.52		
q42	0.61	q85	0.44	q128	0.47		
q43	0.55	q86	0.62	q129	0.56		

Table 1 revealed the difficulty range from about 0.39 to 0.68, with some variation in between. Based on common interpretations of difficulty indices in psychometric testing, items with difficulty indices above 0.60 such as q2(0.65), q4(0.65), q6(0.62), q9(0.62), q11(0.61), q14(0.61), q16(0.64), etc. are relatively easier for most test-takers, however, the respective indices of the items revealed that they still lie within “good and accepted” difficulty range. In the same vein, items with difficulty indices close to 0.20 such as q130(0.39) and q133(0.37) are more difficult than other items however, they are still good and accepted for inclusion into P-SAT. In general term, the average difficulty index of P-SAT is approximately 0.535. This therefore, suggests that the items are, on average, moderately

difficult on P–SAT. This value is a good indicator that the P–SAT has an excellent level of difficulty, with items that are neither too easy nor too hard.

Research Question 2: *What is the discrimination index of P–SAT?*

Table 2: Discrimination index of P–SAT

Item	Discrimination	Item	Discrimination	Item	Discrimination	Item	Discrimination
q1	0.0924	q44	0.4738	q87	0.3340	q130	0.3121
q2	0.6232	q45	0.6631	q88	0.6295	q131	0.5283
q3	0.2931	q46	0.3651	q89	0.1667	q132	0.3189
q4	0.7012	q47	0.6297	q90	0.7151	q133	0.3184
q5	0.1847	q48	0.2959	q91	0.6723	q134	0.6382
q6	0.5955	q49	0.3340	q92	0.4156	q135	0.3194
q7	0.5070	q50	0.6975	q93	0.7209	q136	0.5821
q8	0.3709	q51	0.3998	q94	0.1707	q137	0.3032
q9	0.5835	q52	0.7975	q95	0.4406	q138	0.5056
q10	0.1604	q53	0.4331	q96	0.2704	q139	0.5124
q11	0.5405	q54	0.6339	q97	0.2357	q140	0.4000
q12	0.2891	q55	0.7249	q98	0.6825	q141	0.6174
q13	0.1602	q56	0.4276	q99	0.2448	q142	0.3038
q14	0.6896	q57	0.7453	q100	0.5753	q143	0.6304
q15	0.1952	q58	0.2307	q101	0.3358	q144	0.4102
q16	0.7526	q59	0.5101	q102	0.4987	q145	0.6221
q17	0.2129	q60	0.2772	q103	0.7028	q146	0.1877
q18	0.6914	q61	0.3533	q104	0.5070	q147	0.4786
q19	0.6615	q62	0.7456	q105	0.7472	q148	0.1688
q20	0.4462	q63	0.3513	q106	0.3279	q149	0.2158
q21	0.6798	q64	0.6747	q107	0.4699	q150	0.5965
q22	0.2741	q65	0.1655	q108	0.3175	q151	0.1588
q23	0.4587	q66	0.7465	q109	0.2652	q152	0.6111
q24	0.2941	q67	0.6790	q110	0.6841	q153	0.0883
q25	0.2919	q68	0.5008	q111	0.3774	q154	0.4297
q26	0.7586	q69	0.7378	q112	0.6248	q155	0.5576
q27	0.3815	q70	0.2503	q113	0.2458	q156	0.2192
q28	0.7319	q71	0.6294	q114	0.6192	q158	0.0996
q29	0.3426	q72	0.3228	q115	0.5687	q159	0.5653
q30	0.5166	q73	0.2732	q116	0.2922	q160	0.3998
q31	0.7259	q74	0.7795	q117	0.6400	q161	0.5375
q32	0.4047	q75	0.2470	q118	0.2290	q162	0.3293
q33	0.7098	q76	0.6949	q119	0.6003		
q34	0.3079	q77	0.3681	q120	0.2775		
q35	0.6341	q78	0.6671	q121	0.2279		
q36	0.2809	q79	0.6983	q122	0.5194		
q37	0.1835	q80	0.4445	q123	0.3086		
q38	0.7816	q81	0.7318	q124	0.6454		
q39	0.3903	q82	0.1776	q125	0.2595		
q40	0.6954	q83	0.5754	q126	0.6578		
q41	0.2822	q84	0.2768	q127	0.6656		
q42	0.7544	q85	0.2972	q128	0.4323		
q43	0.6687	q86	0.6421	q129	0.6464		

Psychometric analysis in Table 2 showed that items like q4 (0.7012), q7 (0.5070), q16 (0.7526), q18 (0.6914), etc. have high discrimination values. These items are excellent at differentiating between test-takers who perform well and those who do not. Items with poor discrimination values included item q5 (0.1847), q10 (0.1604), q13 (0.1602) q37 (0.1835), q65 (0.1655), q82 (0.1776), q89 (0.1667), q94 (0.1707), q146 (0.1877), q148 (0.1688), q151 (0.1588), and q158 (0.0996), are poorly discriminating and therefore, not effective at distinguishing between high and low scorers. However, 92.6% of the items of P–SAT have shown acceptable, good or excellent discrimination with discrimination indices mostly ranging from 0.2 to 0.4 and above respectively. P–SAT generally has an

average discrimination value of 0.451. This indicated that P-SAT has an excellent discrimination, hence, has an excellent ability to differentiate between high, average and low scoring students.

Research Question 3: *What is the distracter efficiency of P-SAT?*

Table 3: Distracter Efficiency of P-SAT

Item	Distracter					Item	Distracter				
	A	B	C	D	E		A	B	C	D	E
q1	0.30	0.10	0.10	*	0.10	q82	0.10	0.10	*	0.10	-0.10
q2	0.10	*	0.20	0.00	0.00	q83	0.10	0.10	-0.10	*	0.20
q3	*	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.10	q84	*	0.10	0.10	0.20	0.20
q4	0.00	0.00	*	0.00	0.00	q85	0.10	*	0.10	0.20	0.10
q5	*	0.20	0.20	0.00	-0.10	q86	0.20	0.10	*	0.10	0.10
q6	*	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.20	q87	0.10	0.10	0.10	*	0.10
q7	-0.70	*	0.40	0-10	0.20	q88	0.30	0.00	0.10	*	-0.10
q8	-0.10	-0.30	-0.10	0.00	*	q89	0.10	0.10	0.10	-0.10	*
q9	*	-0.10	0.10	0.00	0.00	q90	*	0.20	0.10	0.10	0.10
q10	0.20	*	0.10	0.10	-0.10	q91	0.10	*	0.10	0.10	0.10
q11	*	0.20	0.10	0.00	0.10	q92	0.10	*	0.10	0.10	1.10
q12	0.40	0.10	*	0.10	0.00	q93	0.20	0.10	*	0.10	-0.20
q13	0.10	*	0.20	0.10	0.10	q94	0.10	0.10	*	0.00	0.10
q14	0.00	0.10	*	0.40	0.00	q95	0.10	*	0.10	0.10	0.10
q15	0.10	*	0.20	-0.10	-0.10	q96	*	0.10	0.00	0.10	0.00
q16	0.20	0.10	0.00	*	-0.10	q97	0.00	0.10	0.00	*	0.00
q17	*	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.20	q98	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.20	*
q18	0.10	0.30	*	0.10	0.10	q99	0.10	0.10	*	0.10	0.10
q19	0.10	*	0.10	0.20	0.20	q100	0.10	*	0.10	0.00	0.10
q20	0.10	0.10	*	0.10	0.00	q101	0.39	0.10	0.10	*	0.10
q21	0.10	0.10	0.00	0.10	*	q102	0.00	0.10	*	0.10	0.10
q22	0.39	0.10	0.10	*	0.10	q103	*	0.2	0.20	0.10	0.10
q23	0.00	0.10	*	0.10	0.10	q104	0.10	*	0.20	0.10	0.10
q24	*	0.2	0.20	0.10	0.10	q105	0.10	*	0.10	0.10	0.10
q25	0.10	*	0.20	0.10	0.10	q106	0.00	0.10	*	0.10	0.10
q26	0.10	*	0.10	0.10	0.10	q107	0.30	0.10	0.10	*	0.10
q27	0.00	0.10	*	0.10	0.10	q108	0.10	0.10	*	0.10	0.20
q28	0.30	0.10	0.10	*	0.10	q109	-0.10	0.10	0.20	*	0.10
q29	0.10	0.10	*	0.10	0.20	q110	0.10	*	0.10	0.10	0.10
q30	-0.10	0.10	0.20	*	0.10	q111	*	0.10	0.00	0.10	0.10
q31	0.10	*	0.10	0.10	0.10	q112	*	0.20	0.10	0.10	0.20
q32	*	0.10	0.00	0.10	0.10	q113	0.10	0.20	*	0.00	0.10
q33	*	0.20	0.10	0.10	0.20	q114	*	0.20	0.10	0.10	0.10
q34	0.10	0.20	*	0.00	0.10	q115	0.00	0.00	*	0.00	0.00
q35	*	0.20	0.10	0.10	0.10	q116	0.10	0.10	0.00	*	0.10
q36	0.00	0.00	*	0.00	0.00	q117	0.10	0.10	0.10	*	0.10
q37	0.10	0.10	0.00	*	0.10	q118	0.20	0.10	0.10	0.10	*
q38	0.10	0.10	0.10	*	0.10	q119	*	0.20	0.10	0.30	0.10
q39	0.20	0.10	0.10	0.10	*	q120	0.10	*	0.10	0.20	0.10
q40	*	0.20	0.10	0.30	0.10	q121	0.10	0.10	*	0.20	0.10
q41	0.10	*	0.10	0.20	0.10	q122	*	0.20	0.10	0.10	0.10
q42	0.10	0.10	*	0.20	0.10	q123	*	0.20	0.10	0.10	0.20
q43	*	0.20	0.10	0.10	0.10	q124	*	0.20	0.10	0.10	0.10
q44	*	0.20	0.10	0.10	0.20	q125	0.00	*	0.00	0.00	0.10
q45	*	0.20	0.10	0.10	0.10	q126	*	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10
q46	0.00	*	0.00	0.00	0.10	q127	0.10	0.10	*	0.10	0.10
q47	*	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	q128	0.10	0.10	*	0.10	0.10
q48	0.10	0.10	*	0.10	0.10	q129	0.10	0.10	0.10	*	0.00
q49	0.10	0.10	*	0.10	0.10	q130	*	0.10	0.10	0.00	0.00
q50	0.10	0.10	0.10	*	0.00	q131	0.10	*	-0.10	0.10	0.10
q51	*	0.10	0.10	0.00	0.00	q132	0.00	*	0.00	0.10	0.00
q52	0.10	*	-0.10	0.10	0.10	q133	0.10	0.10	*	0.10	0.00

q53	0.00	*	0.00	0.10	0.00	q134	0.10	0.10	0.10	*	0.00
q54	0.10	0.10	*	0.10	0.00	q135	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	*
q55	0.10	0.10	0.10	*	0.00	q136	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	*
q56	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	*	q137	0.10	0.10	0.10	*	-0.20
q57	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	*	q138	0.20	0.10	*	0.20	0.20
q58	0.10	0.10	0.10	*	-0.20	q139	0.10	0.10	0.00	*	0.10
q59	0.20	0.10	*	0.20	0.20	q140	0.10	*	0.10	0.10	0.10
q60	0.10	0.10	0.00	*	0.10	q141	0.10	*	0.10	0.10	1.10
q61	*	0.10	0.10	0.10	-0.10	q142	0.20	0.10	*	0.10	-0.20
q62	0.10	*	0.00	0.00	0.00	q143	0.10	0.10	*	0.00	0.10
q63	0.00	*	0.00	0.10	0.00	q144	0.10	*	0.10	0.10	0.10
q64	0.10	0.10	*	0.10	0.10	q145	*	0.10	0.00	0.10	0.00
q65	0.10	0.10	0.10	*	-0.10	q146	0.00	0.10	0.00	*	0.00
q66	0.10	0.10	0.10	*	0.20	q147	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.20	*
q67	0.10	0.10	0.10	*	-0.10	q148	0.10	0.10	*	0.10	0.10
q68	0.10	*	0.10	0.10	-0.10	q149	0.10	*	0.10	0.00	0.10
q69	0.20	0.10	*	0.10	0.00	q150	0.39	0.10	0.10	*	0.10
q70	0.20	0.10	0.10	*	0.00	q151	0.00	0.10	*	0.10	0.10
q71	0.10	0.10	*	-0.10	0.00	q152	*	0.2	0.20	0.10	0.10
q72	0.10	*	0.10	0.10	-0.10	q153	0.10	*	0.20	0.10	0.10
q73	*	0.10	0.10	0.20	0.10	q154	0.10	*	0.10	0.10	0.10
q74	*	0.20	0.10	0.10	-0.10	q155	0.00	0.10	*	0.10	0.10
q75	0.10	0.10	0.00	*	0.10	q156	0.30	0.10	0.10	*	0.10
q76	0.20	*	0.10	0.10	0.20	q158	0.10	0.10	*	0.10	0.20
q77	0.10	0.10	*	0.10	0.20	q159	-0.10	0.10	0.20	*	0.10
q78	0.10	0.10	0.10	*	0.10	q160	0.10	*	0.10	0.10	0.10
q79	0.10	0.10	*	0.10	0.00	q161	*	0.10	0.00	0.10	0.10
q80	0.00	*	0.20	0.00	0.00	q162	*	0.20	0.10	0.10	0.20
q81	*	0.10	0.00	-0.10	0.10						

Table 3 showed 648 distracters from a total of 162 items. Findings from the distracter analysis on the items of P-SAT showed items q4 (0.00), q36 (0.00) and q115 (0.00) with 100% nonfunctional distracter efficiencies. These items had all 4 of its distracters as nonfunctioning which indicates no student selected it. Items q5, q7, q8, q10, q15, q16, q30, q58, q61, q65, q67, q68, q71, q72, q74, q81, q82, q83, q88, q89, q93, q109, q131, q137, q142, and q159 had a negative distracters, suggesting that high-ability students mistakenly selected it. These items should be carefully reviewed, as nonfunctioning distracters do not serve their purpose of differentiating between lower and higher ability students. Negative distracters are especially problematic, as they mislead higher-ability students into choosing an incorrect answer.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In the study, result revealed that P-SAT has a difficulty index of 0.53. This shows that P-SAT generally has an excellent difficulty index. This is based on the guidelines in Hotui (2006, as cited in Butakor, 2022) which established that an item is “good and accepted” when its difficulty index falls within 0.20 to 0.90. It is regarded as “excellent and usable” when its difficulty index is within 0.40 to 0.60. Its termed “difficult and should be reviewed or rejected”, when its difficulty level is less than 0.20 and considered “too easy and to be reviewed or rejected” when its difficulty index is greater than 0.90. This revealed that none of the items of P-SAT is too difficult or too easy. This is inconsistent with findings in Obilor and Obubere (2020) which reported that 12 of its 70 items in social studies cognitive achievement test developed for junior secondary three (JS3) students in Rivers State are not adequate for inclusion. It is also at variance with Al-Ameer (2023) which reported 20 as difficult and 54 easy with only 226 out of the total 300 MCQs analyzed.

Findings from the psychometric analysis showed that P-SAT generally has an excellent discrimination value of 0.451 with no negative values. Results also indicated that items like q4 (0.7012), q7 (0.5070), q16 (0.7526), q18 (0.6914), etc. have high discrimination values. These items are excellent at differentiating between test-takers who perform well and those who do not. However, it revealed that 12 items which included item q5 (0.1847), q10 (0.1604), q13 (0.1602) q37 (0.1835),

q65 (0.1655), q82 (0.1776), q89 (0.1667), q94 (0.1707), q146 (0.1877), q148 (0.1688), q151 (0.1588), and q158 (0.0996) which is 7.4% of the 162 items are discriminating poorly and therefore, not suitable for inclusion into P-SAT. This is based on the guidelines in Teli and Nilesh (2022). This result is similar to Sharma (2021) which had most of its items excellently discriminating above 0.40. The result also reaffirmed the position of Al-Ameer (2023) which revealed 69 (23%) acceptable discrimination, 66 (22%) good discrimination and 55(18.3%) excellent discrimination and with no negatively discriminating item out a total of 190 questions. This is however, inconsistent with Asamoah and Ocansey (2019) which revealed 2 negatively discriminating items with 1 item showing a 0 discrimination from a 30 Multiple Choice Mathematics Technical Report Items.

Findings from the 648 distracter analysis on the 162 items of P-SAT showed items q4 (0.00), q36 (0.00) and q115 (0.00) with 100% nonfunctional distracter efficiencies. These items had all 4 of its distracters as nonfunctioning which indicates no student selected it. Items q5, q7, q8, q10, q15, q16, q30, q58, q61, q65, q67, q68, q71, q72, q74, q81, q82, q83, q88, q89, q93, q109, q131, q137, q142, and q159 had a negative distracters. Negative distracters are essentially problematic, as they mislead higher-ability students into choosing an incorrect answer. These 29 (17.901%) items did not qualify for inclusion into P-SAT. This finding reaffirmed the position of Mahjabeen et al. (2018) in which out of a total of 260 distractors, 72% were functional and only 28% were non-functional while a total of 16 MCQs had zero nonfunctional distracter. This is however in divergence with Butakor (2022) which revealed 30.8% of functional distracters and 69.2% nonfunctional distracters.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the psychometric analysis conducted, P-SAT revealed a difficulty index of 0.53. This indicated that P-SAT generally has an excellent difficulty index. It further revealed that none of the items of P-SAT was too difficult or too easy. Analysis showed that P-SAT generally has an excellent discrimination value of 0.451 with no negative values. Results also indicated that most of the items of P-SAT have high discrimination indices and are excellent at differentiating between test-takers who perform well and those who do not. However, it revealed that 12 items which included item q5 (0.1847), q10 (0.1604), q13 (0.1602) q37 (0.1835), q65 (0.1655), q82 (0.1776), q89 (0.1667), q94 (0.1707), q146 (0.1877), q148 (0.1688), q151 (0.1588), and q158 (0.0996) which is 7.4% of 162 items are discriminating poorly and therefore, not suitable for inclusion into P-SAT. Findings from the 648 distracter analysis on the 162 items of P-SAT showed items q4 (0.00), q36 (0.00) and q115 (0.00) with 100% nonfunctional distracter efficiencies. Item q5, q7, q8, q10, q15, q16, q30, q58, q61, q65, q67, q68, q71, q72, q74, q81, q82, q83, q88, q89, q93, q109, q131, q137, q142, and q159 have negative distracters. These 29 (17.901%) items did not qualify for inclusion into P-SAT.

However, 12 items which included item q5, q10, q13, q37, q65, q82, q89, q94, q146, q148, q151, and q158 which are discriminating poorly, 3 items which included item q4, q36 and q115 with nonfunctional distracter efficiencies and 26 items which included item q5, q7, q8, q10, q15, q16, q30, q58, q61, q65, q67, q68, q71, q72, q74, q81, q82, q83, q88, q89, q93, q109, q131, q137, q142, and q159 with negative distracters did not qualify for inclusion into P-SAT. Therefore, a total of 36 (22.22%) items out of the 162 did not qualify to be listed into P-SAT. Thus P-SAT was reduced to a total of 126 items.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this research, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Biology teachers in Taraba State should use P-SAT as a valid and reliable question bank for future assessment of experimental skills among students in secondary schools across Taraba State.
- ii. The 36 items of P-SAT which do not meet the required cut-off psychometric conditions should be discarded or revised and psychometrically analyzed before they can be used in assessing experimental skills of Biology students.
- iii. Test experts in Taraba State should educate Biology teachers on the need to perform psychometric estimations on test instruments for assessment of experimental skills thereby minimizing the effects of challenges posed by total lack or insufficiency of laboratory apparatuses in Biology Laboratories.

- iv. School authorities and administrators should train and encourage teachers to make use of the procedure adopted in this study to enable them perform psychometric estimations on test instruments for assessment of experimental skills of secondary school students in Taraba State.

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